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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Description (short)
<p>The PEDR designs the strategy so that the outcomes of the ENLIGHT RISE project become available to the different 'end user' groups that can benefit from it.</p> <p>As the project is fully embedded in an overall European University Alliance, ENLIGHT, which already designed a Dissemination and Communication Strategy (Deliverables E+ WP7- D7.11 & WP7-7.1), the document below is an update of this strategy by incorporating ENLIGHT RISE elements.</p>

Quality Control:

Checked by	Name	Affiliation	Date
Co-coordinator WP1&7	Delfien Cloet	UGent	04/06/2021
Executive Secretary	Gijs Coucke	UGent	28/05/2021
Communication Coordination Team		UGent / UGOE / UU / UBx	02/06/2021
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The partners in the alliance are UNIVERSITEIT GENT (GHENT UNIVERSITY – BELGIUM, BE) – UGent (999986096) – COORDINATOR; UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX (UNIVERSITY OF BORDEAUX – FRANCE, FR) – UBx (949735440) – BENEFICIARY & CO-COORDINATOR; UNIVERZITA KOMENSKÉHO V BRATISLAVE (COMENIUS UNIVERSITY BRATISLAVA – SLOVAKIA, SK) – UK BA, also known under CU (999841566) – BENEFICIARY; UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO/ EUSKAL HERRIKO UNIBERTSITATEA (UNIVERSITY OF THE BASQUE COUNTRY – SPAIN, ES) – UPV/EHU (999865234) – BENEFICIARY; OLLSCOIL NA HÉIREANN, GAILLIMH (NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, GALWAY – IRELAND, IE) – NUI GALWAY (999978045) – BENEFICIARY; GEORG-AUGUST- UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS (UNIVERSITY OF GÖTTINGEN – GERMANY, DE) – UGOE (999845640) – BENEFICIARY; RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN (UNIVERSITY OF GRONINGEN – THE NETHERLANDS, NL) – RUG (999989782) – BENEFICIARY; TARTU ÜLIKOOL (UNIVERSITY OF TARTU – ESTONIA, EE) – UT (999895013) – BENEFICIARY; UPPSALA UNIVERSITET (UPPSALA UNIVERSITY – SWEDEN, SE) – UU (999985029) – BENEFICIARY.

To promote a sustainable future and address complex societal challenges, the ENLIGHT universities closely engage with their surrounding socio-economic environments, to connect learners and academic staff, companies and business incubators, governments and policy makers, and civil society actors. Therefore, the respective cities and regions are important Associated Partners of the ENLIGHT network. Further, ENLIGHT calls upon the specific expertise of associated partners for creating the digital campus, for outreach and for developing its comprehensive impact assessment model. Associated partners of the alliance are: BAN KI-MOON CENTRE FOR GLOBAL CITIZENS (AT), CITY OF BORDEAUX/BORDEAUX MÉTROPOLE (FR), CITY OF BRATISLAVA (SK), CITY OF GHENT (BE), CITY OF GÖTTINGEN (DE), CITY OF GRONINGEN (NL), CITY OF TARTU (EE), COMMUNITY GHENT (BE), DATA AND IT-COMPETENCE CENTRE GÖTTINGEN - GWDG (DE), DONOSTIA INTERNATIONAL PHYSICS CENTER (ES), ESET-SLOVAK INTERNET SECURITY COMPANY (SK), EUSKAMPUS (ES), EUSKO JAURLARITZA/GOBIERNO VASCO - EJ/GV (ES), GALWAY CITY COUNCIL (IE), GALWAY COUNTY COUNCIL (IE), GRONINGEN DECLARATION NETWORK (NL), INNOVATIONCAMPUS SNIC (DE), NEW AQUITAINE REGIONAL COUNCIL (FR), NEW ENERGY COALITION (NL), RECTORATE OF THE BORDEAUX ACADEMY (FR), REGION GOTLAND (SE), TECNALIA (ES) AND UPPSALA KOMMUN (SE). The content of this document is the result of discussions within the **ENLIGHT** alliance as a whole.

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Executive Summary

The Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results (PEDR) designs the strategy so that the outcomes of the ENLIGHT RISE project become available to the different 'end user' groups that can benefit from it.

The European university alliance ENLIGHT has two different projects, which both depend on different funding instruments of the European Commission, namely 1) the ENLIGHT E+ project funded by EACEA (Erasmus+), and 2) the ENLIGHT RISE project funded by REA (H2020). However, when communicating towards external stakeholders, the alliance strives to avoid referring to ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE as two different projects but rather speaks of ENLIGHT as an alliance with an education component and since 2021, a research component adding up with new type of actions.

As the ENLIGHT E+ Project already designed a Dissemination and Communication Strategy (Deliverables WP7- D7.11 & WP7-7.1) in July 2021, this document is an update of that strategy by incorporating ENLIGHT RISE elements.

This document outlines the planning of the dissemination and communication activities to be carried out by the alliance to effectively manage ENLIGHT's visibility, raise awareness and understanding of ENLIGHT's activities, share ENLIGHT's outcomes and results.

As described in the Proposal-SEP-210643715 (E+WP7-D7.11): ***"The ENLIGHT Dissemination Strategy defines the use of different media and information packages (content) to reach specific target groups of ENLIGHT, as well as the organisation of specific dissemination events."***

ENLIGHT's initial analysis of dissemination and communication goals is given, strategic plans to address those goals are presented together with implementation measures. Initial mission, vision and key messages are worded that all partners promote and convey through described communication channels. The D&C Strategy includes the 'Digital Marketing Strategy' (E+WP7-D7.1) that describes ***"the connection between the ENLIGHT website and the use of social media accounts and channel, and its relation to the corporate communication accounts and channels of the ENLIGHT partners"***.

The D&C Strategy tackles two main aspects at hand – dissemination and communication, though recognizing the overlap and cross-cutting measures that arise from planning such activities:

- **Dissemination measures** focus on transferring know-how, good practices, success stories and promoting take-up and use of outcomes and results, such as their contribution to European policies and consequent development and progress of European education, through usage of all available channels for promotion.
- **Communication measures** aim to enhance visibility, raise awareness and understanding of all ENLIGHT activities and its presence at various local, regional, national, European and global events.

Internal communication among ENLIGHT alliance partners and detailed procedures are listed and described in the 'Communication Management Strategy' (E+WP1-D1.2) and the Project Communication Plan (RISE WP9 – D. 9.4) and rules for its efficient implementation set out – in order not to hinder any alliance developments.

This D&C Strategy is available to all partners through the ENLIGHT SharePoints:

<https://ugentbe.sharepoint.com/teams/Group.PR202006996/Work%20Packages/WP7A%20Dissemination/Dissemination%20Strategy>

[https://ubordeauxfr.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/Enlight-](https://ubordeauxfr.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/Enlight-Rise/Ressources/Communication/Dissemination_Strategy_PEDR?csf=1&web=1&e=IHegB0)

[Rise/Ressources/Communication/Dissemination_Strategy_PEDR?csf=1&web=1&e=IHegB0](https://ubordeauxfr.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/Enlight-Rise/Ressources/Communication/Dissemination_Strategy_PEDR?csf=1&web=1&e=IHegB0)

Keywords

Dissemination, Communication, Mission, Vision, Key messages, Target Groups, Outcomes, Results, Communication Channels, Awareness, Visibility, Website, Social Media, Newsletter, Info Packages, Open Access, Events, Exploitation, Mass Media.

Abbreviations

& - and

AV - Audio Visual

CA - Consortium Agreement

Alliance Partner - Partner Institution, also referred to as Beneficiary and Party to the Consortium Agreement or Consortium Partner or Corporate Partner

Dx.y - Deliverable numbered, for example D8.2

D&C Strategy - Dissemination and Communication Strategy

GA - Grant Agreement

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

EAB – External Advisory Board

EACEA - Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency

EEA - European Education Area

EC - European Commission

ENLIGHT - European University Network to promote Equitable Quality of Life, Sustainability, and Global Engagement through Higher Education Transformation

ENLIGHT 5 Flagship Areas - Health and Well-being, Digital Revolution and Impact of Digitalisation, Climate Change, Energy and Circular Economy & Equity

ERA – European Research Area

EU - European Union

EUI - European Universities Initiative

EUN - European Universities Networks

HE - Higher Education

IPR - Intellectual Property Rights

KPI - Key Performance Indicators

Mx - Month, for example M12 refers to month 12

OA - Open Access

REA - European Research Executive Agency

TGs - Target Groups

WG - Working Group

WP - Work Package (followed by a number)

1 Introduction

The Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results (PEDR) designs the strategy so that the outcomes of the ENLIGHT RISE project become available to the different 'end user' groups that can benefit from it.

The European university alliance ENLIGHT has two different projects, which both depend on different funding instruments from the European Commission: 1) the ENLIGHT E+ project funded by EACEA (E+), and 2) the ENLIGHT RISE project funded by REA (H2020). However, when communicating towards external stakeholders, the alliance strives to avoid referring to ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE as two different projects but rather speaks of ENLIGHT as an alliance with an education component and since 2021, a research component adding up with new type of actions.

As the ENLIGHT E+ Project already designed a Dissemination and Communication Strategy (Deliverables WP7- D7.11 & WP7-7.1) in July 2021, the PEDR document is an update of this strategy by incorporating ENLIGHT RISE elements. In the text below, it will be referred as the Dissemination and Communication Strategy.

The Dissemination and Communication Strategy's (D&C Strategy) main purpose is to describe the strategy and general timeline to facilitate creating awareness about the vision, mission, concepts, outcomes and results developed throughout the duration of the ENLIGHT alliance. This D&C Strategy identifies the main dissemination activities and communication channels, together with measures, messages and plans of monitoring KPIs and WP deliverables dissemination fulfilment. The strategy set out here is based on the Proposal-SEP-210643715 and Grant Agreement (ENLIGHT GA n°101004027) signed with the EC EACEA and the Grant Agreement (ENLIGHT RISE GA n°101035819) signed with the EC REA. This deliverable provides a description of the strategy adopted by the ENLIGHT alliance to ensure successful dissemination of the outcomes and results of the alliance.

This document is an active document and will be updated when needed or whenever additional key information becomes available. It will, as the ENLIGHT alliance progresses, provide more details for activities planned in the following years. The main principles of dissemination and communication as set out in the definitions of the European Commission will be respected and detailed in this plan:

communication – has started prior to the outset of the action and will continue throughout its entire lifetime – has been coordinated accordingly so that all alliance partners carry the same message; it shall be continuous, creative and encourage dialogue, and its efforts shall be active and outreaching in nature

while the **dissemination** activities will be coordinated among all alliance partners and WP leads to achieve the best visibility of alliance outcomes and results through implementation vehicles defined in this D&C Strategy.

Two main aspects of these activities, which can overlap substantially, are:

- Creation and maintenance of the awareness of the alliance
- Dissemination of alliance outcomes and results

Although it is a separate activity and not part of the D&C Strategy, the activities related to 'exploitation' of outcomes and results are inextricably linked to dissemination and communication.

Figure 1: EC definitions of 'Communication', 'Dissemination' & 'Exploitation'

Creation and maintenance of the awareness and understanding of the alliance: The main aim of this activity is to make the ENLIGHT TGs aware of the alliance. As a 'European University', the communities targeted by ENLIGHT include the students, learners, teachers, researchers & administrative staff, companies & business incubators, governments & policy makers, and civil society actors, while simultaneously communication efforts should be directed at achieving recognisability for ENLIGHT work and achievements with the wider public. The central communication medium is the website. Additional means of communicating ENLIGHT work, other than various social media accounts and channel, will include preparing and designing materials such as posters, flyers and other hand-out materials. An important aspect of this activity is also creation and continuous update of the 'Info packages' to enable wider coverage

with key messages on the alliance. The means and methods for creating and maintaining awareness and understanding about the alliance will be updated throughout the existence of the alliance, ensuring continuity in the presentation and announcement of the alliance's progress.

The dissemination of the results of the alliance is planned through continuous activities managed by the WPs such as organizing events, participating in regional, European and global conferences, international Higher Education (HE) promotional events and publishing in mass media but equally HE specific journals and magazines. This will enable sharing outcomes of ENLIGHT objectives and achievements with the wider community, including surrounding socio-economic environments, to connect students, learners & academic staff, researchers, companies & business incubators, governments & policy makers, and civil society actors, while at the same time receiving feedback from the relevant TGs.

Specific objectives of ENLIGHT dissemination and communication activities can be summarised as follows:

- To build and maintain awareness and understanding of the alliance;
- To stimulate and invite target groups to take part in ENLIGHT activities;
- To build and consolidate relationships between the alliance and specific TGs (students, learners & academic staff, researchers, companies & business incubators, governments & policy makers, civil society actors);
- To stimulate the demand of the new innovative solutions developed within ENLIGHT;
- To ensure the collaboration with related regional socio-economic environments, ENLIGHT flagship area environments and EC, EEA, EUI & HE environments;
- To support the 'dissemination & exploitation' of the alliances' outcomes and results by consolidating alliance visibility among TGs at local, regional, national, European and global levels;
- To establish bridges between the regional policy makers, the national governments, the EUNs and at the EU level, the EEA-EUI but equally with other future dissemination and exploitation worlds;
- To attract 'investors' for the continuous development of learning, teaching and research innovative solutions based on the ENLIGHT flagship areas.

The overall reach and activities of ENLIGHT are not isolated: they are immersed in a context of a wider European Union strategy related to the European Education Area (EEA) and the European Research Area (ERA) through its European Universities Initiative (EUI) and its developmental plans.

The ENLIGHT alliance aligns its goals and monitors policy outputs from the EEA-European Universities Initiative. In November 2017, the European Commission set out a vision for a European Education Area to be built by 2025 "in which learning, studying and doing research would not be hampered by borders". This vision was further concretized - in January 2022 - through the Commission Communication on a European strategy for universities and the Proposal for a Council Recommendation on building bridges for effective European higher education cooperation. The EUI is a flagship initiative of the EEA/ERA. It will enable a new

generation of Europeans to cooperate across languages, borders and disciplines, developing a strong European identity.

Naturally, this means all of ENLIGHT's dissemination and communication efforts will be aligned with the EEA/ERA-EUI activities and ENLIGHT will be present in European Commission activities depending on the schedule of planned events and availability.

2 Strategies

2.1 Time-related Phases

The analysis of ENLIGHT activities clearly defines several time-related phases that we identify as background for D&C Strategy planning:

- **Initial phase of the pilot period:** alliance activities are initiated but no results can be expected.
- **Mid phase of the pilot period:** alliance has reached development phase, some preliminary outcomes and results are available, roadmaps are more defined, preparations for implementation are under way.
- **Final phase of the pilot period:** ENLIGHT GA n°101004027 and ENLIGHT RISE GA n°101035819 results are available; evaluations of results are under way.

Based on all the above, we have identified three phases during the pilot period with related dissemination and communication strategies:

2.1.1 Phase 1: building awareness and understanding

Communication: During the initial phase of the pilot period, the D&C Strategy focuses on 'communication' support around the alliance. The strategy activities are planned with the goal of raising awareness and understanding of ENLIGHT's vision & mission and stimulating participation in initiated activities and organised events activities.

2.1.2 Phase 2: establishing collaborations, stimulating take-up of results, transferring know-how

Communication & Dissemination: During the second phase of the pilot period, when preliminary results start becoming available, the D&C Strategy will focus on 'dissemination' support by providing information about ENLIGHT outcomes and results (WP deliverables), good practices & success stories, and transferring know-how. The strategy will be adapted, refocused if needed and expanded to EC, EEA, ERA, EUI & HE-targeted events where preliminary outcomes and results can be promoted. The D&C Strategy will stimulate the demand of new innovative solutions being developed within the ENLIGHT alliance and initiate collaboration with related environments, equally ENLIGHT flagship area environments. 'Communication' support will be continuous.

2.1.3 Phase 3: consolidate relationships, support exploitation of results, set stage for future work

Exploitation: Finally, in the last phase of the pilot period, the D&C Strategy will focus on supporting 'exploitation' of alliance outcomes and results by extending impact and

contributing to local, regional, national & European policies in EC, EEA, ERA, EUI & HE domains, equally ENLIGHT flagship area domains, by consolidating relationships between the alliance and specific target audiences (students, learners & academic staff, researchers companies & business incubators, governments & policy makers, civil society actors) and by introducing of the next phases of the alliance.

2.2 Key Messages

Below are some initial ENLIGHT key messages that will be communicated throughout the alliance development as well as targeted messages for ENLIGHT key groups of audiences.

2.2.1 Visionary Image

The ENLIGHT visionary image formed basis to develop the ENLIGHT mission and set out an action timeline:

'Imagine you were a student or researcher in any one of the nine ENLIGHT universities and could automatically gain lifelong access to the best courses, teachers and facilities across these institutions and across disciplines. In each of these nine universities, you would be guided through a wide range of opportunities in our digitally interconnected campus. Together with ENLIGHT top-academics and regional actors, you would be involved in solving some of the most complex societal issues facing Europe and the World today (such as climate change, social inequalities, threats to health and well-being, renewable energy supply, and the digital revolution) and empowered to become an engaged global citizen. You would be supported by a variety of mobility schemes to move between countries, and you could take part in sessions transferred around the globe in real-time. During your studies, you would work closely with international peers, acquiring first-hand experience of developments in the broader research world, guided by leading scientists and experts from across Europe. You would be supported to engage into impactful, innovative mission-oriented research and to develop leadership and entrepreneurial skills. Soon after you started you would obtain a first micro-degree, and later on, a joint ENLIGHT degree highly valued by international employers that would make you proud to be an ENLIGHT alumnus and would stimulate you to come back for further learning experiences throughout your life.'

2.2.2 Mission

ENLIGHT's mission can be summarized as 'a **fundamental transformation of European Higher Education** by **empowering learners as globally engaged citizens** with state-of-the-art **knowledge, skills, and innovation potential** to tackle the major societal transition and to promote **equitable quality of life** and **sustainability**'.

- ENLIGHT contributes to the transformation of the European Higher Education.
- ENLIGHT is a truly European university network, tackling existential challenges of a sustainable future: Health & Well-being, Impact of Digitization, Climate Change, Energy & Circular Economy and Equity.
- ENLIGHT aims to transform the way these global challenges are addressed by embedding a societal view into state-of-the-art research and education.

- ENLIGHT will help shape a future-proof education, and research geared towards societal impact.
- ENLIGHT stands for excellence in scientific research & innovation.
- ENLIGHT merges state-of-the-art knowledge and innovation to tackle major societal transitions.
- ENLIGHT promotes equitable quality of life and sustainability in our future cities, communities and beyond.
- ENLIGHT empowers learners and researchers across Europe to become globally engaged citizens.
- ENLIGHT has strong commitment to positive European values and global awareness.
- ENLIGHT establishes the foundations of an integrated European University System with free movement of students, learners, researchers and staff, sharing their resources.
- ENLIGHT "Thinks Global, Acts Local".

2.2.3 Supporting Key Messages

- ENLIGHT is at the forefront of global HE innovative teaching and learning solutions and global state-of-the-art research.
- Collaboration with ENLIGHT is an enabler for future innovative teaching, learning and research exploration.
- ENLIGHT is contributing to new innovative ecosystems by providing new state-of-the-art research solutions and efficient teaching and learning approaches.
- ENLIGHT will empower students, learners and researchers with the necessary knowledge and skills to become globally engaged European citizens, able to tackle societal challenges
- ENLIGHT's outcomes and results bring efficient solutions for the overall competitiveness of European Higher Education and European Research Area.
- European Higher Education will leverage ENLIGHT to bring to competitive teaching, learning and innovative research solutions.
- ENLIGHT's innovative European Higher Education and research offers, facing major societal challenges, will help students, learners & academic staff' European mobility, employment access and capabilities.
- ENLIGHT can contribute to policy making with its regional academies, cities associated partners, EAB members and Think Tank – Core Groups members' expertise.
- ENLIGHT creates a way for young scientists/engineers to develop innovative research around the 5 flagship areas.
- Curricula within ENLIGHT provide competitive knowledge for future major societal challenges.
- Collaboration with ENLIGHT enables pooling of various resources.
- Collaboration with ENLIGHT achieves better visibility to all included.
- Collaboration with ENLIGHT provides pathways for more learners and researchers.
- ENLIGHT will help Europe valorise its identity and values.

- European youth, HE, research, innovative industry, economy, society in its whole and global challenges will benefit from ENLIGHT.
- ENLIGHT contributes to the evolution of an integrated European university system without barriers for learning, teaching, research and innovation between the partner universities.

In addition to the above general messages, specific messages will be designed at appropriate times during alliance development based on results obtained and current status of the global HE environment. Special EUI-EUN-oriented analysis will be continuous to be able to adapt the D&C Strategy accordingly.

2.3 Target Audience

In order to secure success in creating awareness and engaging audience in understanding and using ENLIGHT outcomes and results, the focus of the alliance's dissemination and communication efforts aim at all ENLIGHT TGs.

TG engagement is the key to success of any dissemination and communication initiative, and TG identification is the first and foremost important task in effective engagement. One of the main tasks of ENLIGHT is thus to define and address TGs according to their interests, needs and drivers.

In order to achieve effective dissemination and communication, it is necessary to understand TG motivations. This will enable the ENLIGHT alliance to effectively engage, communicate with and promote future dialogue between different TGs. Indeed, the combination of the TGs' relevance to ENLIGHT and motivations will help to define specific communication strategies for different TGs.

The target audiences for ENLIGHT alliance dissemination and communication have been grouped into five different categories, namely the ENLIGHT Community (internal), Civil Society Actors & General Public (external), Public Bodies (external), Private Sector (external), and Policy Makers (external).

Figure 2: ENLIGHT Internal & External Target Groups

TARGET GROUPS	LEVELS	SUBGROUPS	
ENLIGHT Community	Internal to ENLIGHT & 9 partner institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students Teachers - Academia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers Administrative Staff
Civil Society Actors & General Public	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learners Individual Citizens Citizen Organisations Other Education Experts-Practitioners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-profit Association Sector NGOs Foundations & Charities Other Operators (5 flagship areas)
Public Bodies	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cities & Municipalities Regional Authorities National Authorities European Commission Authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Funding Operators Other EUNs (+ 'FOREU'; 'FOREU2') Other HE Public Operators Other Public Operators
Private Sector	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industries & Companies Technology Developers & private research institutes Business Incubators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private Funding Operators Press & Mass Media Other Professionals
Policy Makers	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HE & Academia Planning Operators Research Planning Operators Other Planning Operators (5 flagship areas) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permitting Bodies Regulators Standardisation Bodies

Table 1: ENLIGHT Target Groups, Levels & Subgroups

The main dissemination and communication strategies that are implemented towards these five TGs and 32 subgroups are as follows:

Target Groups \ Strategies	ENLIGHT Community	General Public	Public Bodies	Private Sector	Policy Makers
Enhance visibility	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Creating awareness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Stimulating participation in events & activities	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Providing information on outcomes & results	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sharing good practices & success stories	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Transferring know-how	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Fostering collaboration & creating opportunities		✓	✓	✓	
Extending impact / valorisation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Contributing to policies			✓		✓
Support HE development			✓		✓
Promoting benefits	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 2: D&C Strategies per Target Groups

The dissemination and communication activities also address the European Commission public policy perspective, by considering main aspects such as:

- Transnational cooperation in a European Consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible);

- Learning and teaching excellence;
- Scientific research and innovation excellence;
- Promote civic engagement;
- Contributing to competitiveness and to solving societal challenges;
- Impact on everyday lives (e.g. creation of jobs, development of new innovative learning methods and technologies, better life-quality, etc.);
- Contributing to developing a strong European identity and promoting European values.

3 Implementation

For the implementation of earlier defined ENLIGHT D&C strategies, several dissemination and communication means and tools (D&C implementation vehicles) have been selected for maximum effectiveness, depending on the TGs, that are described in the following sections.

Target Groups Impl. Vehicle	ENLIGHT Community	General Public	Public Bodies	Private Sector	Policy Makers
Corporate video	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Project website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletter	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Social media – Twitter	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media - LinkedIn	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media – YouTube	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press Media		✓	✓	✓	✓
Communication events	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
WP events	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 3: Target Groups per D&C Implementation Vehicle

3.1 Implementation Management

The 'Communication Coordination Team' (UGent, UBx, UGOE & UU) helps design and implement dissemination and communication actions around ENLIGHT activities and is at disposal of WP leaders to help ask the right questions: 'why, what, to whom, how, and when'.

Figure 3: Implementation D&C Model

The main tasks of the 'Communication Coordination Team' are as follows:

- Identifying and informing about dissemination opportunities (e.g. events, publications, etc.);
- Providing relevant information and documentation to update and enrich the alliance website;
- Posting news and alliance outcomes and results in social media;
- Managing press releases and information campaigns at European and global levels;
- Presenting the alliance at relevant national and international conferences, workshops and other events;
- Supporting the promotion and organisation of ENLIGHT events, in particular engaging key stakeholders to act as multipliers and to motivate participants;
- Updating the alliance management tool (e.g. SharePoint) with all relevant dissemination activities and opportunities;
- Updating the D&C Strategy.

Under the overall management of the 'Communication Coordination Team', all alliance partners (E+ 'WP7 Dissemination WG' and the RISE 'WP9 Management, Dissemination & Exploitation') are contributors to the dissemination and communication activities and more specifically with regards to contents of the website and newsletter. The 'Communication Coordination Team' is the editorial team for the website, newsletter and social media accounts & channel.

As regards to ENLIGHT event organisation, communication events are organized by the 'Communication Coordination Team' and activity events are organised by the concerned WPs.

3.2 Implementation Schedule

During phase 2, regular meetings between the 'Communication Coordination Team' and the WP leaders will determine what WP deliverable documents, relevant to the different TGs that need to be disseminated and the appropriate implementation vehicles. **A D&C content calendar per WP will be established to determine the adequate timing of outcome and result dissemination.**

3.3 Implementation Vehicles

3.3.1 Visual Identity

The development of a visual identity and an alliance logo ensures alliance outputs are consistent and easily recognisable. ENLIGHT logo (voted by the 'ENLIGHT Community' on December 5, 2019) is and will be consistently used in all alliance documents and communication materials. It is accompanied by a '[brand book & graphic chart](#)' to facilitate the consistent usage.

Figure 4: ENLIGHT Alliance Logo, Colours & Significance

➤ **Cover slide**

➤ **Cover slide with logos**

➤ **Chapter title slide**

➤ **Closing slides**

"Like a lighthouse guiding sailors to shore, the ENLIGHT alliance will guide students to become lifelong learners and agents-of-change ready to tackle the challenges of tomorrow"

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

Thank you for your attention
 Ākerikā tāko āure āmātoariki
 Bedankt voor uw aandacht
 Těmno věd věděčnicku věst
 Merci pour votre attention
 Vielen Dank für Ihre Aufmerksamkeit
 Ge neth-meth eger as ds eind
 Þakujum ykk þessum
 Grazie per la presenza
 Tack för din uppmärksamhet

Figure 5: ENLIGHT PPT Template

Usage of the logo should be introduced into all channels of communication and ENLIGHT events or events in which ENLIGHT participates in addition to materials, including all platforms, ENLIGHT website and social media accounts and channel, any form of written/online communication, to ensure visual branding of the alliance and develop a coherent complement to ENLIGHT’s communications that would ensure recognisability in the present and future.

We refer to Article 22 of the ENLIGHT Grant Agreement N°101004027 and Article 38.1.2 of the ENLIGHT RISE Grant Agreement N°101035819, on promoting the action and visibility of EU funding: any communication activity must display the EU emblem with acknowledgement of EU funding, as well as a disclaimer (cf. 3.5.2)

3.3.2 Alliance Partners Institutional Logos & Display with ENLIGHT Logo

The ENLIGHT alliance brings together nine comprehensive, research-intensive universities from nine European countries (Belgium, Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, The Netherlands, Slovakia, Spain, and Sweden). Since the creation of the alliance, the ENLIGHT logo has been displayed and associated to the nine alliance's partner institutional logos. The terms of use and IPR of the aforementioned logos must be respected.

As regards to display, when associated to the ENLIGHT logo, the order preference goes for an alphabetical order following the city (or country – e.g. Basque country) geographical location name in English language, such as presented in the 'ENLIGHT corporate video'.

Figure 6: ENLIGHT & Alliance Partners' Logos Display

The alliance partners' institutional logos, IPR and terms of use can be found through the following links:

- University of the **Basque Country** (UPV/EHU): <https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/gizartea/upv-ehuren-logo-orokorrak>
- University of **Bordeaux** (UBx): <https://www.u-bordeaux.fr/Universite/L-universite-de-Bordeaux/Identite-visuelle/Le-logotype> & [file:///C:/Users/adorin100p/AppData/Local/Temp/2017_Chartegraphique v3_BD.pdf](file:///C:/Users/adorin100p/AppData/Local/Temp/2017_Chartegraphique_v3_BD.pdf)
- Comenius University **Bratislava** (UK BA, also known under CU – attention: logos may not be used by third parties without the consent of the UK BA): *To download logos of the Comenius University Bratislava and its components, you need to log in the intranet.*
- National University of Ireland **Galway** (NUI Galway): <http://www.nuigalway.ie/media/press/NUI-Galway-Brand-Book.pdf>
- **Ghent** University (UGent): <https://styleguide.ugent.be/?lang=en>
- University of **Gottingen** (UGOE): <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/589410.html>
- University of **Groningen** (RUG) (attention: preferred variant is the horizontal logo / to download logo need to go through portal): <https://www.rug.nl/about-ug/practical-matters/huisstijl/huisstijl-basiselementen/logo/?lang=en> & <https://www.rug.nl/about-ug/practical-matters/huisstijl/huisstijl-basiselementen/kleuren> & <https://www.rug.nl/about-ug/practical-matters/huisstijl/huisstijl-basiselementen/logo/gebruik-het-logo-goed>
- University of **Tartu** (UT) (attention: preference round logo): <https://www.ut.ee/en/university/logos> & https://www.ut.ee/sites/default/files/www_ut/tartu_ylikool-logo_ja_v2rvid-cmyk-08_copy.png

- **Uppsala University (UU)** (attention: "Clear zone"):
<https://mp.uu.se/en/web/info/stod/kommunikation-riktlinjer/grafiskarikt/logotyp>

The Governing Board will decide on a visual endorsement of ENLIGHT membership in their corporate branding: websites, corporate presentations and videos, email signatures etc.

3.3.3 Corporate Video

The ENLIGHT corporate video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ePIBbZ1Fumw>) can be downloaded from the ENLIGHT alliance management tool (Office 365 UGent SharePoint) and data-sharing repository, available to all partners, or viewed and embedded from the ENLIGHT YouTube channel (described hereafter).

All alliance partners have contributed to the corporate video and approved the video in its whole before publication. The first public viewing was shown during the official opening session of the ENLIGHT Kick-off Week that took place from March 1 to 5, 2021.

The purpose of the corporate video, made for online distribution, is primarily for promoting and creating awareness about ENLIGHT and targets all alliance's audiences. It can be used as presentation meeting material (i.e. ENLIGHT DemoDays) to introduce ENLIGHT to the alliance partners' students, teachers, researchers, administrative staff, local stakeholders but equally during the WP events (i.e. 1st ENLIGHT Regional Academies, European Dialogues, Global Dialogues).

Figure 7: ENLIGHT Corporate Video

The content of the video (script, footage and text) reflects the ENLIGHT identity and mission statement and depicts and outlines the diverse opportunities the alliance has to offer to students, learners, researchers, staff, and the broader society of European citizens. The corporate video's impact key messages are:

- ***“ENLIGHT will help shape a future-proof education and research, geared towards societal impact.”***
- ***“Our mission: To ENLIGHT, Our Pathway: Transformation through the power of Education, Science and Cooperation”***

The corporate video is embedded in the ENLIGHT website (described hereafter) homepage and social media accounts. **The alliance partners are strongly encouraged to embed it in their dedicated institutional ENLIGHT website pages and social media accounts in national language.** National language subtitles can be added to the ENLIGHT corporate video.

3.3.4 Website

The ENLIGHT public alliance website (E+ WP1-D1.4 & WP7-D7.2 and RISE WP9-MS24), hosted on UGent server, is managed through the 'Joomla!®' 3.9 software which is a website content management system (CMS) for publishing web content, is regularly updated (quarterly updates on average), and is located at <https://enlight-eu.org>

The website, managed in compliance with GDPR regulations, represents the **central medium and channel for dissemination and communication**, and offers relevant tailor-made content and resources to all ENLIGHT TGs. As a primary communication tool, the website address features in all alliance's communication material.

The purpose of the website is to proactively promote the alliance, as a whole, its' activities, and to disseminate its results and outcomes by providing targeted information to various audiences within and beyond the alliance's own community.

The specific goals of this key dissemination and communication channel are:

- to raise awareness about the objectives of the alliance, its outcomes and results, its benefits, use and applicability;
- to share ENLIGHT experience (data & knowledge) with TGs and other stakeholders;
- to seek the support of authorities, lobbies, policy makers and the general public;
- to build understanding and facilitate adoption of alliance outcomes and results;
- to assure that all interested parties are involved, participate and are informed about the status of the alliance and its events;
- to connect the ENLIGHT community.

Figure 8: ENLIGHT Website

Preliminary communication content has been provided on the basis of the Proposal-SEP-210643715, the ENLIGHT RISE Grant Agreement N°101035819 and the ENLIGHT mission statement. The ENLIGHT website structure covers general information on the alliance, description of the alliance partners, major streams of activities & actions, headings/categories webpages dedicated TGs (e.g. 'For Students', 'Research & Innovation', 'For Cities and Communities'), communication materials such as the embedded ENLIGHT corporate video or downloadable fact sheets in national languages tailored to different TGs and shares 'contact' information respectful of the ENLIGHT governance structure. In addition, the ENLIGHT website contains a 'calendar to communicate on 'open-to-public' relevant ENLIGHT events and registration. The website equally hosts an **ENLIGHT partner search form** and an **ENLIGHT promotional friendly-user search tool for (pilot) courses**.

Dissemination material is dependent on the WP outcomes and results (ref. '3.1 Implementation Management').

The 'news & events' section contains articles on ENLIGHT activities, news and alliance partners' news relevant to the ENLIGHT alliance and activities.

Three types of activities with 'news value' to certain TGs in and outside ENLIGHT's university communities are distinguished:

- **Type 1:** ENLIGHT project outcomes (events, learning activities ...)
- **Type 2:** Initiatives between ENLIGHT partners (outside project scope)
- **Type 3:** Individual partner initiatives

In order to manage the massive information flow and to avoid confusion among TGs, a distinction is made between 'ENLIGHT news' (containing types 1 and 2) and 'Partner news' (type 3). Both categories receive separate news feed on the ENLIGHT website.

Even though, 'ENLIGHT news' receives priority in terms of visibility (front page, listing) and for sharing on social media.

As for the unilateral initiatives from one of the ENLIGHT partners: the ENLIGHT alliance considers that all opportunities for students/researchers/staff can be communicated through the ENLIGHT website, if relevant to the ENLIGHT community. Hence, ENLIGHT communication vehicles should be open as much as possible and not restrictive. Alliance partners should be offered the opportunity to promote their offer to the other alliance partners. However, it is understood that alliance partners should not promote or market their own university through ENLIGHT. Therefore, the selection criterion regarding the alliance members' unilateral initiatives that have 'news value' is that the concerned initiatives should contain a **certain offer towards the other alliance partners in order to be labelled as ENLIGHT**: waiving of fees for the ENLIGHT community (e.g. students, teachers, researchers, administrative staff) and learners, a free scholarship for the ENLIGHT students and learners, a specific call for participation addressed to the ENLIGHT alliance partners, etc. Unilateral initiatives which do not meet this criterion can still have their separate section on the ENLIGHT media under 'Partner news', within limits determined by the editorial team in order to maintain balance between alliance partners.

Finally, alliance partners should make use of the ENLIGHT website dissemination and communication document repository as the reference source for **public digital content on ENLIGHT that can be downloaded by interested public (TGs)**.

Other alliance communication tools such as the newsletter, fact sheets, flyers.. will refer to the ENLIGHT website and ENLIGHT social media accounts and channel whenever possible, to ensure that the public visits the latter on regular basis and gets used to it as a concise and trustworthy source of information on various ENLIGHT events and activity outcomes and results. Conversely, the ENLIGHT website incorporates the newsletter, social media links from ENLIGHT's accounts and channel, to help boost visibility of those communication means, accounts and channel through the website.

3.3.5 Alliance Partners Institutional ENLIGHT Website Pages in National Language

ENLIGHT alliance partners are strongly encouraged and have engaged through the ENLIGHT CA to link to their corporate communication channels whenever appropriate, at their own online websites, social media accounts and channels and through their corresponding newsletters.

Each alliance partner has provided a dedicated, permanent page about ENLIGHT on their respective institutional websites (in national language and/or English):

- University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU): <https://www.ehu.eus/eu/web/europeanprojects/-/erasmus-project-enlight>
- University of Bordeaux (UBx): <https://www.u-bordeaux.fr/enlight>
- Comenius University Bratislava (UK BA, also known under CU): <https://uniba.sk/medzinarodne-vztahy/enlight/> & <https://uniba.sk/en/international-relations/enlight/>
- National University of Ireland Galway (NUI Galway): <http://www.nuigalway.ie/enlight>
- Ghent University (UGent): <http://www.ugent.be/enlight> & <https://www.ugent.be/en/ghentuniv/principles/internationalisation/enlight.htm>
- University of Gottingen (UGOE): <http://www.uni-goettingen.de/enlight>

- University of Groningen (RUG): <https://www.rug.nl/about-ug/profile/internationalization/networks/>
- University of Tartu (UT): <https://www.ut.ee/et/ulikoolist/enlight> & <http://ut.ee/enlight>
- Uppsala University (UU): <https://mp.uu.se/sv/web/info/vart-uu/internationella-natverk/enlight> & <https://mp.uu.se/en/web/info/vart-uu/internationella-natverk/enlight>

The alliance partners' institutional ENLIGHT website pages in national language are part of the information packages tailored to different TG's (E+WP7-D.7.3). The institutional weblinks will be provided in the format "*institutionalwebsite/enlight*".

Content guideline for the institutional webpages: ENLIGHT logo, ENLIGHT vision and mission, the main actions, partners, internal contact persons, link to ENLIGHT website and social media account, link to the newsletters subscription, corporate video and the translated fact sheet.

3.3.6 Newsletter

The ENLIGHT newsletter is built-in app on the Joomla! CMS software. It comprises images and teaser texts linked to the articles published on the website, hence a digest of the most important news items of the website. The newsletter therefore respects the same selection criterion for publishing news and articles as the website. It is sent out by email to subscribers through the institutional ENLIGHT emails (e.g. "enlight@institutionalname.country") for the ENLIGHT community subscribers and directly through the website for the external subscribers to attract attention to the website and present the main info on a regular basis (every 3 months) to the TGs.

The newsletter is managed in compliance with the GDPR requirements. Therefore, the interested audience may subscribe exclusively through the ENLIGHT website at: <https://enlight-eu.org/index.php/university-about-us/about-enlight/newsletter>

Figure 9: ENLIGHT Newsletter

Figure 10: ENLIGHT Newsletter Subscription Website Page

3.3.7 Social Media

Social media are gaining increasing popularity nowadays and therefore it is another important dissemination channel. The ENLIGHT alliance believes this is a powerful awareness-raising communication tool aimed towards the general public, and the presence of the alliance on major social networking platforms has been established from the early stages of the alliance. The purpose of social media (WP7-D7.1 & WP7-D7.2) is to proactively promote the alliance and its final outcomes and results permitting a two-way exchange. ENLIGHT's presence in social networks aims to accomplish the following specific objectives:

- Generate awareness and multiply the communication efforts done by all partners;
- Raise interest on the alliance topics in non-expert audiences;
- Promote understanding of knowledge, activities, benefits and outcomes generated through the alliance lifecycle;
- Promote feedback gathering, consultation and engaging with TGs;
- Increase content visibility and interaction;
- Enhance alliance positioning through engine search, image search, local search, etc.

ENLIGHT will use Twitter (as leading forum for connecting, branding and for conversation), LinkedIn (as leading professional B2B platform) and YouTube for video content. Facebook is less used for professional purposes.

The Student Network has their own channels:

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Enlight-Student-Network-343343546853580>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/enlightstudentnetwork/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/enlightstudent1>

3.3.7.1 Twitter Account

The ENLIGHT Twitter account, available at https://twitter.com/enlight_eu, is managed in compliance with GDPR regulations and used to **inform the broader community about both technical and social information related to ENLIGHT**. Extensive use of Twitter will be continued, as it serves as an efficient communication channel with the general public as well as with EC communities and EUN alliances. Through active Twitter engagement over the alliance lifetime, ENLIGHT will build a network of followers. The ENLIGHT Twitter account is managed by several accounts via *tweetdeck.twitter.com*.

Figure 11: ENLIGHT Twitter Account

ENLIGHT's Twitter account will also be used to link and signpost to other EU initiatives. 'Hashtags' to be used should reflect the various interests ENLIGHT has (EC Youth, EC agencies' news, EUI, other EUNs, EEA, ERA, ENLIGHT flagship challenges, EAB members, HE) as well as links to EC and EU policies. Links and tags will be made to other relevant alliances as appropriate to boost visibility and engagement.

The ENLIGHT Twitter account shall be accompanied by a '**Who to follow guideline**' to facilitate the consistent usage.

3.3.7.2 LinkedIn Account

The LinkedIn platform provides the **opportunity to network, discuss and engage with ENLIGHT community and other interested stakeholders**. ENLIGHT will engage with some of the already established EUNs and will use the platform to connect to relevant stakeholders in all fields relevant to ENLIGHT (e.g. ENLIGHT 5 flagship challenges).

ENLIGHT's LinkedIn page managed in compliance with GDPR regulations is available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/enlight-europeanuniversity>

Figure 12: ENLIGHT LinkedIn Account

The content planned for LinkedIn is informative in nature: ENLIGHT events, ENLIGHT participation in events, ENLIGHT activities, ENLIGHT outcomes and results, news related to EC agencies, EAB members and associated partners and other domains of interest (5 flagship areas) to ENLIGHT alliances members.

3.3.7.3 YouTube Channel

The YouTube platform serves as an **audio-visual repository for ENLIGHT videos** and other AV materials but equally for **live-streaming in open online format for internal and external viewers** in the setting of conferences, workshops and meetings.

ENLIGHT's YouTube channel is available at:

- Channel URL: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAs4YULyi8ZgXsrDIGLg5Rw>
- Custom URL: <https://www.youtube.com/c/ENLIGHTEU>

The channel is managed in compliance with GDPR regulations and is in line with other platforms, used and embedded, if necessary, in the website's homepage and news content page.

Figure 13: ENLIGHT YouTube Channel

Videos from ENLIGHT events (e.g. Kick-off Week event, student network events, doctoral seminars, teaching & learning conferences, Regional Academies, European dialogues, global dialogues, conference on HEI impact assessment, DemoDays per partner location), ENLIGHT activities, ENLIGHT members' presentations at conferences/events (invited talks), interviews, tutorials, etc. are published on the channel either uploaded as ENLIGHT content or linked from other channels (e.g. EC, EUI, etc.).

The ENLIGHT corporate video uploaded to the ENLIGHT YouTube Channel is one of the major communication materials. It is embedded through the ENLIGHT YouTube Channel in the ENLIGHT website and other social media accounts.

ENLIGHT may also link to other available ENLIGHT related video content respecting its usage terms.

3.3.8 Press Releases & Information Campaigns

Radio, television, newspapers (incl. digital) and specialist and technical publications (incl. digital) are conceived as **additional avenues for the promotion of the alliance's objectives, outcomes and results**. Updates on the alliance's progress and targeted messages about offerings to the different TGs are candidates for mass media publication.

Important announcements resulting from the various alliance activities are selected for press releases and submission to professional newspapers as well as sector magazines. Press releases are a very efficient communication tool to inform about relevant milestones or mass events of the alliance. Press releases and information campaigns are published targeting various media to inform about the start and ongoing achievements of the alliance.

The specific goals of this dissemination and communication vehicle are:

- to raise awareness about the objectives of the alliance, its outcomes and results, its benefits, use and applicability;

- to seek the support of the authorities, lobbies, policy makers and the general public;
- to build understanding and facilitate adoption of alliance outcomes and results;
- to assure that all interested parties (TGs) are involved, participate and are informed about the status of the alliance;
- to promote the benefits of European universities to the general public.

The importance of press and media in promotion and coverage of ENLIGHT activities is recognized and appropriate activities are planned to provide continuous support to journalists and representatives of the media.

Figure 14: Examples of ENLIGHT Press Information Campaigns

Alliance partners are in charge of managing the ENLIGHT press releases and information campaigns at local, regional and national levels and are encouraged to keep documents on file or in a repository to be communicated to the 'Communication Coordination Team' for ENLIGHT archiving purposes (e.g. ENLIGHT UGent SharePoint).

At European and global levels, the ENLIGHT press releases and information campaigns are managed by the 'Communication Coordination Team'.

The information packages tailored to different TG's are available to support alliance partners when providing information to journalists and representatives of the media.

The content of the ENLIGHT information distributed to journalists and representatives of the media may contain (non-exhaustive list / can be updated):

- Corporate video (English - national language subtitles can be added)
- Mission statement (English)
- Factsheets (English & national languages) with list and basic reference of all ENIGHT alliance partners included
- Quote sheet (e.g. ENLIGHT Kick-off Week)
- Issued ENLIGHT press releases and key announcements
- Set of digital artwork (digital flyers, digital posters, roll-ups, logo & logo usage terms)

- Pointer to website repository for downloadable digital documents
- List of ENLIGHT contacts for any further inquiry

Important: For releasing overall ENLIGHT alliance 'opinions', 'statements', viewpoints' and 'positioning', all alliance partners must seek approval of the 'ENLIGHT Director's Meeting' and 'ENLIGHT Executive Secretary' through the 'Communication Coordination Team'.

3.3.9 Information Packages & Communication Materials

Information packages tailored to different TG's (E+ WP7-D.7.3) are available in the 11 languages of ENLIGHT (English, German, French, Dutch, Estonian, Swedish, Spanish, Basque, Irish, Slovak, Frisian) to increase awareness among prospective students, parents and citizens connected to our ENLIGHT communities.

All alliance partners contribute to providing and updating the information packages content in the own languages.

All communication materials in information packages tailored to different TG's that can be built under digital format will be made available on the website repository for downloadable digital documents (easily found and effortlessly accessed) and will be the reference source for **digital content on ENLIGHT that can be downloaded by interested public**.

Several communication materials are included in the information packages:

- Corporate video (English - national language subtitles can be added)
- Mission statement (English)
- Factsheets (English & national languages) with list and basic reference of all ENIGHT alliance partners included
- Alliance partners' institutional ENLIGHT website pages (national languages)
- Set of digital artwork (digital flyers, digital posters, logo & logo usage terms - English)
- List of ENLIGHT contacts for any further inquiry

In phase 1, under deliverable E+ WP7-D.7.3, the 'Communication Coordination Team' has focused on the translations of the EU ENLIGHT fact sheet

(<https://ec.europa.eu/education/sites/default/files/document-library-docs/european-universities-factsheet-enlight.pdf>) and on encouraging the alliance partners to create a webpage in the national language on their respective institutional websites.

Where the use of English is more problematic for certain TGs, concerned alliance partners can plan additional measures and translation of more tools, such as the 'ENLIGHT Corporate Video or the 'ENLIGHT Mission Statement'.

ENLIGHT banners and sustainable merchandising will be developed, as well as templates for PowerPoint presentations, flyers etc.

3.3.10 Strategic D&C events

Beyond the use of media means and vehicles to share results of the alliance, ENLIGHT will organise specific strategic dissemination and communication events.

3.3.10.1 Kick-off Week

The ENLIGHT Kick-off Week, held on March 1-5, 2021, was ENLIGHT's premier annual communication event. It was focused to make holistic awareness of ENLIGHT strategic activities, results, goals and future roadmap. The ENLIGHT Kick-off Week offered a fully online programme, comprising an opening and closing session, a round-table discussion between the ENLIGHT alliance rectors and the ENLIGHT external advisors, public lecture sessions on the ENLIGHT flagship areas, a WP5 'Communities and Universities' session aimed towards the ENLIGHT cities associated partners, a WP5 'European Dialogue' to establish the ENLIGHT Think tank, showcase sessions, an ENLIGHT Student Network Pub Quiz on the theme of 'Inclusivity', work sessions, virtual coffee breaks, and evening events, each hosted by one of the nine ENLIGHT alliance partners.

Figure 15: ENLIGHT Kick-off Week Banner

The successful kick-off week brought together more than 50 keynote speakers, academics, experts and students of all ENLIGHT universities, as well as renowned external speakers from various fields.

All sessions excluding the work sessions were open to the general public through links to the Zoom platform (UGOE account) and live streamed through the ENLIGHT YouTube channel. Registration through the ENLIGHT website was mandatory and free. In total, there were 1296 individual registrations (incl. 191 student registrations with PhDs & 129 external registrations other than the ENLIGHT community).

The communication vehicles used for this event were the ENLIGHT website, newsletter, social media, Student Network, the alliance partners' institutional websites, social media & newsletters.

With the help of the alliance partners Communication/PR offices, the kick-off week banner was published on the alliance partners' institutional website homepages, which contributed to a significant rise in registrations.

Figure 16: Kick-off Week Banner on Institutional Alliance Partners' Institutional Homepages

All public ENLIGHT Kick-off Week sessions can be post viewed (4,104 views with 869 views for the corporate video and 167 subscribers at deliverable date – the ENLIGHT YouTube channel was opened and activated for the ENLIGHT Kick-off Week) and used for communication and dissemination purposes at:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLnfet7rb1WLWkDOcMw2eglavmtx6BVJu>

On 27 September 2021, ENLIGHT held its formal kick-off of the RISE project in a virtual format. This event brought together around 170 participants from the ENLIGHT community: Executive Committee members, Project Board members and executive teams (task experts per WP), as well as other interested participants.

3.3.10.2 Demo Days Events

The DemoDays events (E+ WP7-D7.8) are connected to the Regional Academy (E+ WP5-D.5.12) at each ENLIGHT partner and can be connected to an existing event (e.g. Public Science Days, International Week, Science Week).

From year 2 of the E+ project onwards, each ENLIGHT partner will organise an annual regional Demo Day to showcase the work of the ENLIGHT Regional Academies to a broader public and to enhance the participation of citizens and regional organisations.

Such as the Regional Academies, the DemoDays are organised and funded through co-funding contribution (not included in the E+ budget) by each alliance partner.

The first ENLIGHT DemoDays are planned for the course of 2022.

3.3.10.3 Other WP Key Events

As an implementation vehicle for all above mentioned three strategy phases, strategic WP events have been planned:

ENLIGHT E+ WP Key events

WP	Del. N°	Title	Description	D&C Level	Est. Del. Date
WP1	D1.9	3 ENLIGHT General Conferences	Once a year the General Meeting brings together all internal and external ENLIGHT stakeholders. Beyond informing all stakeholders about the state-of-play, the aim of the two-day meeting is to consolidate the broad commitment, and to maintain the dialogue across the different governance layers / The ENLIGHT General Conference in English is a recurrent event (M12, M24, M36), and leads to formal reports with recommendations. The 1st took place during the Kick-off Week.	Public	31/10/2023
WP2	D2.16	5 Doctoral Seminars (1/flagship area)	Learning format, pilot seminars, online/digital education in English / The doctoral seminars involve all partners for organizing/hosting.	Public	31/10/2022
	D2.9	5 Flagship Short Programmes	Problem-based learning format and pilot module, online/digital education in English. Each of the 5 ENLIGHT Think Tank core groups involving all partners will design and test minimum one pilot of a challenge-based ENLIGHT Flagship Short Programme.	Public	31/10/2023
	D2.6	15 ENLIGHT Living Labs (5/year) - Y1, Y2 & Y3	Challenge-based learning format and pilot module, online/digital education in English / All partners organize Living Labs each year (M12, M24, M36)	Public	31/10/2023
WP3	D3.8	Multilingualism Peer Review Cycle	The Peer Review in English is a preparatory process, for knowledge building among experts. It is aimed to launch new networks of expert staff members via blended, thematic Peer Review sessions for peer learning and network creation. 1st cycle of workshops/events in English, structure (cooperation, network creation, peer learning), running from M1 to M12.	Public	31/10/2021
	D3.12	European Identity & Diversity Peer Review Cycle	2nd cycle of Workshops/events in English, structure (cooperation, network creation, peer learning), running from M13 to M24.	Public	31/10/2022
	D3.5	3 Teaching & Learning Conferences (180 p. each)	The Teaching & Learning Conference in English aims at reaching a broader target group, and concludes each peer review cycle, taking place by M12, M24 and M36.	Public	31/10/2023
	D3.1	3 ENLIGHT Global Engagement modules	The Global Engagement module is a learning format in English to enable students and staff to develop awareness and understanding of diversity and inclusiveness. Pilot modules will be organized in M12, M24, and M36. The module will consist of different (off and online) units.	Public	31/10/2023
	D3.15	Leadership & Entrepreneurship Peer Review Cycle	3rd cycle of Workshops/events in English, structure (cooperation, network creation, peer learning), running from M25 to M36.	Public	31/10/2023

WP5	D5.12	ENLIGHT Regional Academies	The Regional Academies are the local structure to set up recurrent events in alliance partners' national languages, meetings, cooperation, network creation (quadruple helix). The Regional Academies will be a forum for identifying the local challenges, and as such giving local input to the Think Tank. Structure, Events (meetings, cooperation, network creation in local context).	Public	Cycles: M6-M12, M18-M24, M30-M36
	D5.1	ENLIGHT European Dialogue - Y1, Y2 & Y3	A preparatory dialogue (ED1) in year 1 was organised during the Kick-off Week. The Think Tank established the work of the core groups integrating relevant local and EU stakeholders. From year 2, the European Dialogues in English will provide an opportunity to gather the key experts from the ENLIGHT Think Tank and Regional Academies and establish a dialogue with other key stakeholders across Europe / Recurrent event in M2, M14, M26.	Public	Y1: 02/03/2021 Y2: 31/12/2021 Y3: 31/12/2022
	D5.3	ENLIGHT Global Dialogue - Y2 & Y3	The Global Dialogues in English are three-day student-driven and student-centred conferences. They unite students, researchers and university leaders from the ENLIGHT universities with important actors from targeted regions of the world / Events (conferences), Outreach activities, recurrent in M16 and M28.	Public	Y2: 28/02/2022 Y3: 28/02/2023
WP6	D6.4	1st Conference on HEI Impact Assessment	The Impact Assessment in English methodology and tools (1.0) will be reviewed by selected external panels, including both HEI and non-HEI experts. Event, Outreach activity.	Public	31/10/2022
WP7 & WP5	D7.8	2 Demo Days per partner location - Y2 & Y3	Recurrent Demo Days, in M16, M28. Each partner will organize 2 demo days in the own city/region for local stakeholders, hence each partner leads own initiative in alliance partners' national languages.	Public	28/02/2022

Table 4: ENLIGHT E+ WP Key Events List & Timing

ENLIGHT RISE WP Key Events List & Timing

WP	Del. N°	Title	Description	D&C Level	Est. Del. Date
WP1	MS2	Online workshop on best practices of RSOs of the 9 universities	Workshop to "Share practices on R&I support activities" for the staff involved in the R&I-SG	For the members of the consortium	30/04/2022
WP2	D2.5	R&I Prize year 1	Annual contest / competition to award Prizes for the best ENLIGHT RISE R&I project/initiative on ENLIGHT flagship challenges conducted by early career researchers from 2 or more ENLIGHT partner universities	Public	30/11/2022
	D2.6	R&I Prize year 2	Annual contest / competition to award Prizes for the best ENLIGHT RISE R&I project/initiative on ENLIGHT flagship challenges conducted by early career	Public	30/11/2023

			researchers from 2 or more ENLIGHT partner universities		
	D2.7	R&I Prize year 3	Annual contest / competition to award Prizes for the best ENLIGHT RISE R&I project/initiative on ENLIGHT flagship challenges conducted by early career researchers from 2 or more ENLIGHT partner universities	Public	31/08/2023
WP3	MS7	Online workshop on connecting with European infrastructures (#1 scoping)	Introduction to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and digital research infrastructures. Takeaways will be a deeper understanding of how users can engage with EOSC.	Public	07/06/2022
	MS8	Online workshop on connecting with European infrastructures (#2 update and lessons learned)	Update and lessons learned	Public	28/02/2023
	MS9	ENLIGHT DI/AI workshops organized by the DI/AI network (#1 DI/AI network alone)	The DI/AI Network will work closely with the digitalization core group of the ENLIGHT Think Tank (Panel 2) and organize 2 ENLIGHT DI/AI workshops (at least in part virtual) on the topic of DI/AI, to contribute to increasing awareness and enable knowledge exchange.	Public	31/12/2022
	MS10	ENLIGHT DI/AI workshops organized by the DI/AI network (#2 with Innovation Network)	One of these workshops will be organized jointly with the ENLIGHT Innovation Network (WP5) to exchange information and best practices on industry-academic partnerships around DI/AI and propose models to optimize the quality of data used for research purposes, to ensure protection of academic freedom when collaborating with DI/AI industries, and to optimize joint governance guidelines.	Public	31/08/2023
WP4	D4.1	Networking events for early career researchers #1	An annual early career researcher networking events will bring together the ENLIGHT doctoral network and early career researcher network.	For the members of the consortium	31/08/2022
	D4.2	Networking events for early career researchers #2	An annual early career researcher networking events will bring together the ENLIGHT doctoral network and early career researcher network.	For the members of the consortium	31/08/2023
	D4.3	Networking events for early career researchers #3	An annual early career researcher networking events will bring together the ENLIGHT doctoral network and early career researcher network.	For the members of the consortium	31/08/2024
		Research Assessment Workshop (#1)	The RA Working Group will share information on research assessment, systems will be compared, best practices will be discussed. Themes discussed will include how to evaluate quality over quantity, how to include Open Science activities,	For the members of the consortium	30/09/2022

			interdisciplinarity, teamwork, entrepreneurship, engagement with and for society, how to reflect diverse career paths (including research, teaching, leadership etc.), and how to foster gender equality and diversity in assessment systems.		
		Research Assessment Workshop (#2)	The RA Working Group will share information on research assessment, systems will be compared, best practices will be discussed. Themes discussed will include how to evaluate quality over quantity, how to include Open Science activities, interdisciplinarity, teamwork, entrepreneurship, engagement with and for society, how to reflect diverse career paths (including research, teaching, leadership etc.), and how to foster gender equality and diversity in assessment systems.	For the members of the consortium	30/09/2023
	MS11	Open Research Assessment Workshop	The Open RA Workshop, not limited to the members of the working group, gathering high-level representatives of the partner universities, policy makers and policy advisors involved in quality management, research policy, HR policy etc. It will present the practical recommendations on possible innovations in the research assessment systems.stated a in the policy document (D4.5).	Public	31/08/2024
WP5	MS12	ENLIGHT AIM-Days #1	Leveraging longstanding experience at UU (https://aimday.se), this alliance-wide ENLIGHT AIM Days will foster and/or strengthen the dialogue between academy, and relevant governments. Specific questions raised by the local governments, and coordinated by the ENLIGHT Innovation Network, will form the meeting day agenda prioritizing topics related to the five ENLIGHT flagship societal challenges. The outcome is a day filled with a series of 'one question, one hour' workshops where multidisciplinary, multistakeholder teams of approximately five to ten experts discuss each topic.	Public	31/08/2023
	MS13	ENLIGHT AIM-Days #2	Leveraging longstanding experience at UU (https://aimday.se), this alliance-wide ENLIGHT AIM Days will foster and/or strengthen the dialogue between academy, industry, and relevant governments. Specific questions raised by the industrial partners, and coordinated by	Public	31/08/2014

			the ENLIGHT Innovation Network, will form the meeting day agenda prioritizing topics related to the five ENLIGHT flagship societal challenges. The outcome is a day filled with a series of 'one question, one hour' workshops where multidisciplinary, multistakeholder teams of approximately five to ten experts discuss each topic.		
WP6	MS14	Kick-off workshop to share results and set up a mentoring scheme	A kick-off workshop will be organized to share results of the Survey of existing civil society engagement tools and projects in research, innovation, teaching, and Learning (D6.1), discuss wider engagement contexts and options, plan, and set up mutual mentoring scheme.	For the members of the consortium	31/08/2022
WP7	MS17	ENLIGHT Open Science Award	To assess and Incentivize Open Science activities, ENLIGHT partners will experiment with an ENLIGHT Open Science Award and report the lessons learned (i.e. concept development with selection criteria and committee, publication and promotion of the call, evaluation of submissions, public announcement of result and further engagement via the OS network).	For the members of the consortium	31/11/2022
		Open Science Workshops	A series of online workshops/webinars targeting researchers and staff that are working on the implementation and promotion of OS practices in their organization will be organized.	Public	31/08/2024
WP8		Training actions	Training of researchers and research support officers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For engaging with non-specialist audiences, policy-makers and business in the promotion of impactful research - For broadening the scope of projects with structured "impact" sections 	For the members of the consortium	31/12/2022 31/12/2023 31/08/2024
		Dialogues with ENLIGHT academics, non-academic staff, policy-makers, industry and relevant societal actors	Specific R&I impact workshop(s) during the ENLIGHT HEI Impact Conference organised in the framework of E+ project	Public	31/03/2023

Table 5: ENLIGHT RISE WP Key Events List & Timing

As mentioned in Task 7.1.1 (of the ENLIGHT E+ project) specific sessions of the ENLIGHT events (e.g. European Dialogues, Global Dialogues, Teaching & Learning Conference, Peer Review Cycles, etc.) will be made available for external participants in open online formats, and/or turned into e-learning resources. For all these events, onsite and/or online sessions (excl. Regional Academies & DemoDays organised in local context - except if recorded - respecting GDPR) will be organised. The major dissemination and communication vehicles that will be

used are the ENLIGHT E+ WP7 online event calendar hosted on the ENLIGHT website and the ENLIGHT E+ WP7 article & video publications on the ENLIGHT website, newsletter and YouTube channel.

3.3.10.4 Participation in national & international fora – educational and/or scientific conferences & promotional events

At the moment of the publication of this deliverable, alliance partners plan to attend national and international fora with the aim of promoting the ENLIGHT alliance or showcase specific ENLIGHT activities, outcomes and results, holding booths and participating in talks at European higher education conferences and promotional events. **A list of concerned events or conferences** will be developed and will by no means be closed and fixed; its purpose is to reflect the best possible venues and events for ENLIGHT to disseminate and communicate the alliance's outcomes and results. The list of concerned events or conferences is meant to be updated, rethought and modified continuously to better encompass all other aspects of dissemination and communication and exploit opportunities that may present themselves during the alliance's life. **Alliance partners are mandated to inform the 'Communication Coordination Team' about all the relevant events they are considering.**

3.4 Planned WP Public Deliverables

Based on the above defined implementation vehicles and key messages, the below table gives the planned WP deliverables to be made public:

ENLIGHT E+ Public deliverables

WP	Del N°	Title	Description	D&C Level	Est. Del. Date
WP1	D1.6	Validated QA Plan	The QA Taskforce will validate a QA plan, which includes the QA protocol, and defines stages of the PDCA cycle, indicators, and risk assessment procedure. Document/Guidelines, Electronic document, English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/01/2021
	D1.18	Common principles for the joint ENLIGHT quality approach	Common principles for the joint ENLIGHT quality approach will be developed, following the analysis of the existing internal quality assurance systems and practices in the different individual universities, and external QA-procedures (year 1). / Document/handbook/guidelines (Electronic document, English) - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2022
	D1.20	Joint vision on the ENLIGHT University System	A joint vision on the ENLIGHT University System will be developed containing scenarios and timelines for linking structures of the individual universities / Document/guidelines (Electronic document, English) - Future vision communication	Public	31/10/2022
	D1.8	Validated QA reports by QA Taskforce + recommendations	The automated QA reports (see D1.7) need to be validated by the QA taskforce to monitor progress, detect potential problems, and deliver specific recommendations every 6 months (hence M6,M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, Electronic document, English) - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2023

	D1.19	Pilots for the ENLIGHT certification system	Pilots for the ENLIGHT certification system will be developed based on the learning outcomes of the learning formats/modules developed (WP2, WP3) and in connection with the design of the competence framework (WP4). / Document/report/certification system (Electronic document, English) - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2023
	D1.17	Blue-print of permanent ENLIGHT centres – set of recommendations	The blue-print of permanent ENLIGHT centres are a set of recommendations with regard to the structural embedding of the three ENLIGHT inter-university centres (Regional Academies, Teaching and Learning Centre and the QA and Impact Centre). It is part of the Framework Agreement for the implementation of the ENLIGHT University System. Electronic Document, English - Future vision communication	Public	31/10/2023
WP2	D2.1	Calendar & Guidelines for managing the Think Tank core groups	Calendar and Guidelines for managing the Think Tank core groups around the 5 flagship areas. Document, guidelines, online resource , Electronic document/ online tool , English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/01/2021
	D2.7	Map of local challenges existing expertise, projects, learning opportunities	Document, mapping, online resource , Electronic document/database, English / the mapping contains contributions of all partners. - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	30/04/2021
	D2.4	Map of existing expertise, projects, learning opportunities across ENLIGHT	Document, mapping, online resource (database), Electronic document/database, English - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	31/08/2021
	D2.15	Catalogue of ENLIGHT Doctoral Projects & Seminars	Document, catalogue, online resource , Electronic document/database, English - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	31/10/2021
	D2.8	Living lab poster catalogue	Document, online resource , Electronic document/online tool, English - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	31/10/2021
	D2.10	Flagship Short-Programme Learning Outcome Guide	Problem-based learning format and pilot module. Document, guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	30/04/2022
	D2.18	Living Lab Learning Outcome Guide	The Living Lab Learning Outcome Guide will support the design and organisation of the actual Living Lab learning formats, and describes the knowledge and skills that students should have acquired upon completion of the Living Labs. / Document/handbook/guidelines (Electronic document, English) - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	30/04/2022
	D2.11	Guidelines for transfer of practices to other ENLIGHT contexts	Guidelines for transferring the learning formats to other domains of study than the flagship areas. Document, Methodology, Guidelines, Electronic document, English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2022
	D2.12	Joint Degrees: overview of desired learning outcomes	Document, Guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	31/10/2022
		D2.5	ENLIGHT Think Tank annual report	The ENLIGHT Think Tank brings together the key experts, resources, and state-of-the-art research experience and practice of all ENLIGHT universities and regions, and orient them towards addressing challenges in the five chosen flagship areas. The Think Tank will provide recurrent annual reports about the progress of the challenge-based learning activities (M11, M23,	Public

			M35), Electronic documents, English - D&C on outcomes & results		
WP3	D3.9	Map of language learning opportunities	Online resource , mapping, catalogue, Electronic document/database, English - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	30/04/2021
	D3.2	Map of existing learning opportunities in global engagement	Online resource , mapping, Electronic document/database, English - D&C on outcomes & results	Public	30/04/2021
	D3.24	Content design of the Teaching & Learning Conference	The Content Design of the Teaching & Learning Conference defines the format, scope, content, time-frame and desired target groups for the annual Teaching & Learning Conference, which takes place at the end of each thematic teaching and learning cycle. Document/guidelines (Electronic document, English) - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/06/2021
	D3.10	Learning materials & guidelines to integrate multilingual awareness in education practice	Document/Learning materials/guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/07/2021
	D3.3	Content design , architecture of online/offline module units	Content design, architecture of online/offline module units, defining the format, scope, content, time-frame and desired target groups for the Global Engagement module. Document, guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/07/2021
	D3.6	Content design of the Teaching & Learning Lab	Online resource for teachers, Electronic document/database, English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/07/2021
	D3.7	Design assessment and selection procedure Learning & Teaching Award	Document/ guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/07/2021
	D3.20	Map of teacher education exchange opportunities	Online resource /Mapping, Electronic document/database, English - D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/10/2021
	D3.13	Map of best practice approaches in diversity	Online resource , Electronic document/database, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/04/2022
	D3.23	Overview of desired learning outcomes & competencies of the Global Engagement module	The overview of desired learning outcomes and competencies of the Global Engagement module will support the design and organisation of the actual Global Engagement module, and describes the knowledge and skills that students should have acquired upon completion of the module. Document/mapping/guidelines (Electronic document, English) - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/04/2022
	D3.14	Learning materials and guidelines to integrate diversity awareness in education practice	Document/ guidelines, learning materials, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/07/2022

	D3.22	Design joint module for blended learning	Design of a joint ENLIGHT module for blended learning, targeted to teacher education students. Document/guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/10/2022
	D3.17	Map of best practice approaches in Career guidance & Talent Development	Online resource , mapping, Electronic document/database, English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/04/2023
	D3.18	Learning materials for innovation management skills & leadership	Document, learning materials, guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/07/2023
WP4	D4.18	1st Pilot Catalogue of Flexible Mobility Schemes	The 1st Pilot Catalogue of Flexible Mobility Schemes will be a first pilot design for integrating existing and new joint learning formats among the ENLIGHT universities. Online resource (Electronic document/database, English) - D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/10/2021
	D4.1	Mapping of desired components & learning outcomes of the ENLIGHTable curricula	Mapping of desired components and learning outcomes of the ENLIGHTable curricula, as a 1st step in the process of creating modalities for certification. Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results	Public	30/04/2022
	D4.11	Support strategy for reforestation programmes	Support strategy for reforestation and forest protection programmes (in cooperation with international partners) to offset emissions. Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/04/2022
	D4.19	Competence framework for obtaining ENLIGHT certificates and degrees	The ENLIGHT Competence Frameworks defines the learning outcomes for the existing and new learning formats, as listed in the pilot course catalogue (Milestone 12). It also defines the modalities for obtaining certification. Document/handbook/guidelines (Electronic document, English) - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2022
	D4.6	Pilot of success stories	Pilot of case studies to highlight success stories and to set and manage expectations around challenges and the facilitation options available with regard to the mobility of underrepresented groups. Electronic document/ Online content , English - D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/10/2022
	D4.9	Guidelines/Incentives for sustainable mobility (in cooperation with Student Network)	Easy-to-follow guidelines and incentives for sustainable mobility will be designed in cooperation with Student Network. Document/Guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2022
	D4.10	Network for online travel counselling (ticket/dispatch system)	Network for online travel counselling (ticket/dispatch system), using a skilled team of counsellors for online advice about alternatives to emission-intensive modes of transport. Structure/ Online resource/Service, Online tool , English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2022
	D4.12	Carbon calculator	Carbon calculator enabling students/staff to find ways to offset emissions generated by mobility through alternative lifestyle choices. Online resource, Online tool , English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2022
	D4.13	Catalogue of Sustainable Living	Catalogue about sustainable living, matching the specific local conditions at each of the ENLIGHT university cities. Electronic document/ Online content ,	Public	31/10/2022

		English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how		
D4.2	Modalities for ENLIGHT portfolio certification	Modalities for ENLIGHT portfolio certification define how credits can be obtained and accumulated , and eventually could lead to an ENLIGHT degree. Document/guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2023
D4.3	Modalities for micro-credentials	Modalities for micro-credentials comprise the opening up of the ENLIGHT learning formats to a broader group of non-traditional, life-long learners, and related certification for these groups . Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2023
D4.20	Pilot of the Interconnected Campus	The Pilot of the Interconnected Campus will establish and test the connection and inter-operability between the ENLIGHT partners' learning environments and administrative services/infrastructures for the five flagship areas. Online infrastructure (online tool , English) - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2023
D4.7	Design of scholarship strategy	Design of scholarship strategy for creating targeted scholarship funding and establishing targets for mobility of underrepresented groups . Document/Guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2023
WP5	D5.13	Content design & architecture of the European Dialogues	Public	30/06/2021
	D5.4	Content design & architecture of the Global Dialogues	Public	31/08/2021
	D5.6	Mapping of desired learning outcomes for the Global Dialogues	Public	31/08/2021
	D5.5 (& D7.10)	Listing of key partners & cooperation projects outside EU (together with WP7-D 7.10 'Partner portfolio of European and Global partners')	Public	31/10/2021
	D5.7	Global Citizenship Award Framework: criteria & selection, awarding process	Public	31/10/2021

	D5.2	European Dialogue policy recommendations - Y2	European Dialogue Policy recommendations are document/report containing the conclusions from the European Dialogue (see D84) in M14 (and M26), Electronic document, English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/12/2021
	D5.10	European Dialogue policy recommendations - Y3	European Dialogue Policy recommendations are a document/report containing the conclusions from the European Dialogue (see D119) in M26, Electronic document, English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/12/2022
WP6	D6.2	ENLIGHT Impact Assessment Scenario	The ENLIGHT Impact Taskforce will determine the scope of the impact assessment within ENLIGHT for the first 3 years, and select the focus domains of impact for developing the methodology. Document/Guidelines, Electronic document, English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/04/2021
	D6.7	Methodology & toolkit 1.0 for HEI Impact	The Methodology and Toolkit 1.0 for HEI Impact will be the first methodological framework for impact assessment, based on the review of existing practices and development of replicable methods, which is to be tested and further refined along pilot cases by the end of the 3-year period. Document/handbook/methodology (Electronic document, English) - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/04/2022
	D6.5	Methodology & toolkit 2.0 for HEI Impact	The review of the pilot cases will contribute to refining the Methodology and improve the Toolkit 1.0 for impact assessment. Document/Handbook/Methodologies, Electronic document, English - Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2023
	D6.8	Pilot cases' "narratives with numbers" & global report	During the last six months of year 3 each pilot case (in which the impact toolkit was applied) will be reviewed and a comprehensive report will be elaborated in the form of a 'narrative with numbers' that builds on the strength of both metrics and narratives. Report/Data collection/Analyses (Electronic document, English) - D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/10/2023
WP7	D7.10	ENLIGHT Funding plan	ENLIGHT Funding plan (incl. list of prospective national/European funding opportunities, co-funding mechanisms, fund-raising strategy) to inform proactively the ENLIGHT community about funding opportunities that match ENLIGHT activities and deliverables. Online resource , guidelines, Electronic document/ online content , English - D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2021

Table 6: ENLIGHT E+ WP Deliverables for D&C Strategy

ENLIGHT RISE WP deliverables

WP	Del N°	Title	Description	D&C Level	Est. Del. Date
WP1	D1.2	Operational Guidelines and Service offer of R&I-SG	The operational guidelines will describe the services of R&I SG that are available to ENLIGHT partners (example: services to facilitate and incentivize research collaborations, identification of suitable funding	Public	30/06/2022

			support, post-award assistance). Transfer of good practices & know how		
	D1.4	Proposal support kit for researchers	Support kit to researchers to help them build their R&I grant proposal Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	28/02/2023
	D1.6	ENLIGHT R&I-SG Sustainability Report	Report describing the strategy for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the R&I-SG and embedding this structure in the long term ENLIGHT strategy D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2024
WP2	D2.2	R&I Observatory	The ENLIGHT R&I Observatory will act as an online one-stop shop portal centralizing various benchmarking results, surveys, and evidence-based policy recommendations emerging from the project. D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/12/2022
	D2.5	R&I Prize year 1	Annual contest / competition to award Prizes for the best ENLIGHT RISE R&I project/initiative on ENLIGHT flagship challenges conducted by early career researchers from 2 or more ENLIGHT partner universities D&C on outcome & results	Public	30/11/2022
	D2.6	R&I Prize year 2	Annual contest / competition to award Prizes for the best ENLIGHT RISE R&I project/initiative on ENLIGHT flagship challenges conducted by early career researchers from 2 or more ENLIGHT partner universities D&C on outcome & results	Public	30/11/2023
	D2.7	R&I Prize year 3	Annual contest / competition to award Prizes for the best ENLIGHT RISE R&I project/initiative on ENLIGHT flagship challenges conducted by early career researchers from 2 or more ENLIGHT partner universities D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/08/2023
WP3	D3.1	Digital infrastructure mapping & roadmap for sharing and connecting with European digital infrastructures for R&I	The report will map the existing digital research infrastructures prioritizing those of relevance to ENLIGHT global societal flagship challenges, and will propose methods to connect and share identified digital infrastructures across the alliance, with a special focus on infrastructures that are relevant to ENLIGHT flagship challenges D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2022
	D3.2	Map of DI/AI initiatives, tools and methods in ENLIGHT	Map of existing initiatives, tools and methods to describe, analyse, or reinforce the DI/AI policies among ENLIGHT partners, to be posted on the ENLIGHT R&I observatory D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	28/02/2023
	D3.3	Case studies on connecting with European infrastructures for R&I	Create a template and collect information (through online form and/or interviews) from partners to describe the context, integration/linking process and lessons learned. D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/08/2023

	D3.4	White paper for an ENLIGHT responsible DI&AI development Index	The report will describe how ENLIGHT can actively contribute to advancing responsible DI/AI R&I, to optimize its impact on the 5 flagship challenges and develop a responsible DI/AI Development Index to assess and monitor the implementation of these guidelines. D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	29/02/2024
WP4	D4.5	Recommendations on research assessment systems	Policy document providing (practical) recommendations on improving research assessment systems Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	29/02/2024
WP5	D5.1	Map of academy-industry partnerships	Map of academy-industry partnerships related to UN-SDGs & ENLIGHT flagship challenges, available through the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory D&C on outcome & results	Public	31/12/2022
	D5.2	Formalize the ENLIGHT Innovation Network	Report on the formalization of the ENLIGHT RISE Innovation Network : list members, governance structure, agenda D&C on outcome & results	Public	28/02/2023
	D5.3	Recommendations on gaps and opportunities in the market for skills & innovation	The report will identify gaps and opportunities in the market for skills and innovation, which match with common, synergistic R&I skills across the alliance (based on the patent analysis and technology monitoring conducted in WP2). D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2023
	D5.4	Report of methodologies for sparking impactful innovation	Map and benchmarking report of existing initiatives supporting industry-academy collaborations and entrepreneurship in ENLIGHT universities D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2024
WP6	D6.1	Survey of existing civil society engagement tools in Research, Innovation, Learning and Teaching	Survey among ENLIGHT partners to create an overview of existing projects, tools, and needs for efficient and flexible engagement of civil society in research, innovation, and higher education D&C on outcome & results	Public	30/04/2022
WP6	D6.3	Final report on experiences, learning and recommendations for engagement activities with civic society	The final report will make recommendations based on experiences and learnings of WP6 activities D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2024
WP7	D7.1	ENLIGHT Open Science Status Quo & Opportunities #1	Brings together a mapping of OS activities of all partners through an Open Science Status Matrix, highlights good practices, identifies gaps and opportunities for joint action, proposes joint principles, and outlines options for rewards and incentives D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2022

WP7	D7.3	ENLIGHT OA & RDM Starter Kit for Researchers	The Enlight Open Access (OA) and Research Data Management (RDM) Starter Kit will bring together basics arguments and information on how to get started, generic information and information on OA and RDM – where to get started, where are places to get information for example on GDPR, DMPs, data repositories, required policies, licenses etc. Usable templates which can be adapted to local situation and different subject fields Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2023
WP7	D7.2	ENLIGHT Open Science Status Quo & Opportunities #2	The update summarises the engagement activities of T7.1 and T7.1, highlights achievements, points out remaining obstacles and draws conclusions on what worked best in the effort of mainstreaming OS across the ENLIGHT network. Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2024
WP8	D8.1	Web-based repository and tool for mutual learning on R&I impact	Web-based tool that will act as an alive repository of international best practices, as well as ENLIGHT partners' best practices on R&I impact assessment and measurement. D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Confidential at its launch to be made public at the end of the project	31/08/2022 31/08/2024
WP8	D8.4	Report on barriers and opportunities on R&I impact-driven agendas #1	Report on the different workshops, encounters, webinars, surveys, interviews, etc. collecting and analysing the barriers, challenges and opportunities to implement impact-driven R&I agendas D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2024
WP8	D8.5	Report on barriers and opportunities on R&I impact-driven agendas #2	Report on the different workshops, encounters, webinars, surveys, interviews, etc. collecting and analysing the barriers, challenges and opportunities to implement impact-driven R&I agendas D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2024
WP9	D9.2	RISE Project Management Handbook – Guidelines on project management procedures	Guidelines on project management procedures : internal project activity monitoring, quality process for deliverables publication, decision-making process and governance, risk monitoring and management Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/11/2021
WP9	D9.4	Project communication plan	The communication plan will be designed in connexion with ENLIGHT Erasmus+ foreseen activities. It will list the target stakeholders, key messages to be communicated and the means of delivering these messages as well as the partner responsible for leading the communication tasks. Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/10/2021
WP9	D9.3	ENLIGHT RISE data management plan	Data management plan: assessment of data generated and/or existing data used and processed in the frame of ENLIGHT RISE, selection of appropriate and secure repository to make data accessible and re-usable in line with FAIR principles, assessment of full compliance with RGPD for any personal data collection in the frame of the project. Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	28/02/2022

WP9	D9.5	Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results (PEDR)	The PEDR will design the strategy so that the outcomes of the ENLIGHT RISE become available to the different 'end user' groups that can benefit from it. It will consider both the scientific and academic communities (via peer-review publications, conference presentations...), and the non-academic partners and stakeholders of ENLIGHT(-RISE), i.e. industry partners, civil society, governments and other public administrations (e.g. rectorate), international organizations Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	30/04/2022
WP9	D9.6	Policy brief #1	Policy brief summarizing the policy recommendations stemming from all WPs activities D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	28/02/2023
WP9	D9.7	Policy Brief #2	Updated policy brief summarizing the policy recommendations stemming from all WPs activities D&C on outcome & results / Transfer of good practices & know how	Public	31/08/2024

Table 7: ENLIGHT RISE WP Deliverables for D&C Strategy

3.5 Implementation Requirements

3.5.1 Open Access Rules

The ENLIGHT alliance has defined rules for dissemination and those are set forth in the GAs and with special rules set in the Consortium Agreements of both ENLIGHT alliance projects. ENLIGHT views Open Educational, Open Science and Citizen Science resources as key enablers to promote the European Green Deal. All ENLIGHT partners are supportive of and have invested in Open Educational, Open Science and Citizen Science approaches (including Open Source, Open Access to publications, data management and sharing, more transparent peer review, public involvement in academic research, etc.). Outcomes and results will be made available under an open license to facilitate re-use and application.

Exceptions may occur, where due to GDPR, data-protection or other legal issues certain information must remain confidential.

ENLIGHT's education activities will take place in a variety of on-site and e-learning formats. Open Educational Resources (audio-visual and other learning and teaching interactive materials, such as mobile apps) which are created in these contexts will be shared via the ENLIGHT website and released with open licenses to enable massive (re)use. The alliance integrates social media in its D&C strategy to promote ENLIGHT activities, events, and learning opportunities.

ENLIGHT endorses the principles of Open Access for the transfer of knowledge. The ENLIGHT E+ WP2 will monitor and assess the implementation of Plan S (<https://www.coalition-s.org/>). At mid-term, ENLIGHT seeks to create incentives for an Open Science Culture as a basis for the establishment of a broader ENLIGHT research infrastructure. The respective Open Science departments of the ENLIGHT alliance partners will set up a peer review cycle, and have drafted joint actions in support of Open Science, to raise awareness, and to transform the way researchers and other stakeholders create, store, share, and review research outputs. Consequently, scientific publications produced within the project will be made available in

Open Access. Both 'green' and 'gold' Open Access models will be considered, as well as specific Open Access tools developed by ENLIGHT partners will be deposited in OpenAIRE-compliant repositories.

Within the ENLIGHT RISE project, WP 7 is entirely focussed on Open Access, its usage and propagating throughout the alliance. In the medium- to long-term, a joint storage infrastructure for Open Access of ENLIGHT scientific publications and related research data will be developed as part of the European University System.

Furthermore, the ENLIGHT Regional Academies (E+ WP5) will bring together scientists, software developers and educators to collectively develop, manage and utilise (web-based) citizen science projects that will be operationalised in the ENLIGHT Living Labs and Pilot Cases (E+ WP2).

ENLIGHT will mobilise the abilities of a distributed community of citizen scientists through public consultations (surveys and focus groups), participative technological assessments, and community-based research carried out by a larger workforce than academics, including citizen volunteers and students.

In addition, local DemoDays, in cooperation with intermediary organisations, will take place to present the work of the research groups and exhibit social projects (E+ WP7).

3.5.2 GDPR Requirements

The ENLIGHT alliance follows the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation - version of the OJ L 119, 04.05.2016).³ The European Data Protection Regulation is applicable as of May 25th, 2018 in all member states to harmonize data privacy laws across Europe. All ENLIGHT alliance partners are required to respect the European Data Protection Regulation in the context of the ENLIGHT activities.

3.5.2 Acknowledgement of European Union & Erasmus+ Programme Funding

All ENLIGHT dissemination and communication activities must acknowledge the European Union, the Erasmus+ Programme funding (http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/abouteacea/visual-identity_en), and the H2020 SwafS Programme funding, and follow the 'Guidelines for beneficiaries on the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes'.⁴

Moreover, EU funding must be acknowledged in all types of public outputs (including patent applications, EU standardisation of results), media contacts and other public statements.

The preferred option is to acknowledge by quoting: ***"Co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union"***.

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035819".

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035819

Figure 17: European Flag & Acknowledgment Text

When acknowledging the above quote should be accompanied with the European emblem - the 'EU flag' - (if graphical content is applicable) and the name of the European Union spelled out in full in all dissemination, communication and promotional material. The brand names of 'Erasmus+' and 'Horizon 2020' shall not be translated.

The EU flag and funding statement, available in the Grant Agreement (article 22) and on the Europa website, must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence.

Any communication activity related to ENLIGHT must indicate the following disclaimer: *"The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, etc.] represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains."*

3.5.3 Use of the Erasmus + Project Results Platform

An Erasmus+ Project Results Platform⁵ was established to offer a comprehensive overview of projects funded under the E+ Programme and to highlight good practice examples and success stories. The platform also makes available products/deliverables/intellectual outputs, which are the result of the projects funded. The ENLIGHT E+ WP7 UGent coordinator will update this platform.

4 Monitoring & Reporting KPIs

As a part of internal alliance monitoring, the 'Communication Coordination Team' and WP coordinators will also continuously monitor selected KPIs:

ENLIGHT E+ WP KPIs

WP	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	
WP1 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # General Conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Participants per TG in general conferences
WP2 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Living Labs # Short Programmes # Doctoral Seminars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Participants per TG in Living Labs # Participants per TG in Short Programmes # Participants per TG in Doctoral Seminars
WP3 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Global Engagement modules # Peer Review Cycles # Learning & Teaching Conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Participants per TG in GE modules # Participants per TG in Peer Review Cycles # Participants per TG in L&T Conferences
WP5 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Regional Academies # European Dialogues # Global Dialogues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Participants per TG in Regional Academies # Participants per TG in European Dialogues # Participants per TG in Global Dialogues
WP6 Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Impact Assessment Conference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Participants per TG in IA Conference
WP7 Events & Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Google Analytics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Social Media Followers & Subscribers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Internal/External Website Users • # Website Publications • # Website Publications Hits • # Newsletter Subscriptions • # D&C Material Downloads • # Events with Online Dissemination • # DemoDays 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Social Media Posts/Tweets/Updates • # Social Media Hits (impressions likes, shares, retweets) • # Live streams/Webinar/Post views • # Contributions at International Conferences • # Participants per TG in local DemoDays
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Table 8: List of KPIs per ENLIGHT E+ WP related to D&C Monitoring

ENLIGHT RISE WP KPIs

WP	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	
WP1 Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Workshop on best practices of RSOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Participants per TG in workshop on best practices of RSOs
WP2 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # focus groups established • # R&I Prizes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # partners involved in each focus group • # Participants per TG in R&I Prizes
WP3 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # workshops on connecting with European infrastructures • # DI/AI workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Participants per TG in workshops on connecting with European infrastructures • # Participants per TG in DI/AI workshops
WP4 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking events for early career researchers • # Research Assessment Workshop • # Open Research Assessment Workshop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Participants per TG in Networking events for early career researchers • # Participants per TG in Research Assessment Workshop • # Participants per TG in Open Research Assessment Workshop
WP5 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # AIM-Days 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Participants per TG in AIM-Days
WP6 Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Workshop on Civil Society Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Participants per TG in Workshop on Civil Society Engagement
WP7 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Open Science Award • # Open Science Workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Participants per TG in Open Science Award • # Participants per TG in Open Science Workshops
WP8 Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Training Actions • # R&I Impact Workshop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Participants per TG in Training Actions • # Participants per TG in R&I Impact Workshop
WP9 Events & Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google Analytics • # Internal/External Website Users • # Website Publications • # Website Publications Hits • # Newsletter Subscriptions • # D&C Material Downloads • # Events with Online Dissemination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # Social Media Followers & Subscribers • # Social Media Posts/Tweets/Updates • # Social Media Hits (impressions likes, shares, retweets) • # Live streams/Webinar/Post views • Overall # participants to ENLIGHT RISE workshops and (public) events

Table 9: List of KPIs per ENLIGHT RISE WP related to D&C Monitoring

The 'Communication Coordination Team' will collect reports from WP leaders and coordinators on activities done and monitor the execution tempo and timeline for alignment with the D&C KPIs. At the end of each year, the E+ WP7 and RISE WP9 coordinators will compile all the data related to execution of dissemination and communication activities.

5. D&C Strategy Updates

This document is an active document and will be updated when needed or whenever additional key information becomes available:

- Updates according to the progress and emerging outcomes and results of the alliance;
- Updates to consider changes in the alliance, work context, communication materials and potential exploitation of outcomes and results during the alliance's lifetime.

It will, as the ENLIGHT alliance progresses, provide more details for activities planned in the following years. Periodic updates of D&C Strategy will be integral part of the D&C Strategy. The reports submitted will include analysis of each of the communication channels (website, social media, event attendance), activities, outcome and results dissemination efforts and will thus provide data that enables a clear and comprehensive update to the E+ WP7-D7.11 & WP7-7.1 deliverables and to the RISE WP9-D9.5 deliverable.

¹ Annex II Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Programme Guide 2020: https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/sites/default/files/erasmus_programme_guide_2020_v3_en.pdf

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm.

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/communication/services/visual_identity/pdf/use-emblem_en.pdf

⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects/>